

Evaluation of CMIP5 EURO-CORDEX: Precipitation

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November 4, 2025

Table of Contents

Heatmap: Difference from observations	2
Maps: Annual mean difference from observations over Europe	3
Heatmap: Regional average of the percent difference from observations	4
Maps: Annual mean percent difference from observations over Europe	5
Heatmap: RMSE by season and region	6
Heatmap: Change in mean values between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099	7
Maps: Change in annual mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099	8
Heatmap: Change in mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099 relative to 1991-2020	9
Maps: Change in annual mean between 2070-2099 and 1991-2020 relative to 1991-2020	10
Timeseries: Annual mean 1971-2099, grouped by GCM	11

Appendices

Taylor Diagrams	13
Maps: Seasonal mean difference from observations over Europe	15
Maps: Seasonal mean percent difference from observations over Europe	27
Maps: Change in seasonal mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099	39
Maps: Change in seasonal mean between 2070-2099 and 1991-2020 relative to 1991-2020	51

References

We acknowledge the World Climate Research Programme's Working Group on Regional Climate, and the Working Group on Coupled Modelling, former coordinating body of CORDEX and responsible panel for CMIP5. We also thank the climate modelling groups (see Figure 2.7 of Climate CH2025 Scientific Report: <https://www.klimaszenarien.ch>) for producing and making available their model output. We also acknowledge the Earth System Grid Federation infrastructure an international effort led by the U.S. Department of Energy's Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison, the European Network for Earth System Modelling and other partners in the Global Organisation for Earth System Science Portals (GO-ESSP).

We acknowledge the E-OBS dataset from the EU-FP6 project UERRA (<https://www.uerra.eu>) and the Copernicus Climate Change Service, and the data providers in the ECA&D; project (<https://www.ecad.eu>)

Maps: Annual mean difference from observations over Europe

Annual mean differences in precipitation (mm/day) between model simulations and gridded observational estimates in the reference period 1991–2020 displayed as maps for each model simulation. Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Heatmap: Regional average of the percent difference from observations

Regional average of the difference in precipitation between model simulations and observational estimates relative to observational estimates (% of mm/day) in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual) in the reference period 1991–2020. Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Maps: Annual mean percent difference from observations over Europe

Annual mean differences in precipitation between model simulations and observational estimates relative to observational estimates (% of mm/day) in the reference period 1991–2020 displayed as maps for each model simulation. Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Heatmap: RMSE by season and region

Root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) in precipitation for each model simulation compared to observational estimates in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual) in the reference period 1991-2020. Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Heatmap: Change in mean values between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

Regional average change in precipitation (mm/day) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual). Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH).

Maps: Change in annual mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

Change in annual mean precipitation (mm/day) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 displayed as maps over the PRUDENCE Alps region.

pr change 2070-2099 - 1991-2020 [mm/day]

Heatmap: Change in mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099 relative to 1991-2020

Regional average change in precipitation (mm/day) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 relative to 1991-2020 in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual). Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH).

Maps: Change in annual mean between 2070-2099 and 1991-2020 relative to 1991-2020

Change in annual mean precipitation (mm/day) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 relative to 1991-2020 displayed as maps over the PRUDENCE Alps region.

pr relative change 2070-2099 - 1991-2020 [% mm/day of historical]

Timeseries: Annual mean 1971-2099, grouped by GCM

Annual mean timeseries from 1971-2099 in precipitation in Europe and Switzerland (CH) for each model simulation, grouped by driving GCM. Observational estimates from EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland are displayed in black. The effective Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS; °C) for each GCM is displayed in the upper left corner of each figure.

- Model
- CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - IPSL-WRF381P_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - UHOH-WRF361H_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - Observations

- Model
- CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - CNRM-ALADIN63_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - IPSL-WRF381P_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - UHOH-WRF361H_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - Observations

- Model
- CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - CNRM-ALADIN63_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - IPSL-WRF381P_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - Observations

Appendices

Taylor Diagrams

Taylor Diagrams showing RMSE, correlation, and standard deviation in one diagram for all model simulations for precipitation and observational estimates (black star and dashed line) for Europe and Switzerland during the period 1991-2020. Standard deviation is proportional to the radial distance from the origin, correlation is related to the azimuthal angle, and RMSE is proportional to the distance from the observations (grey contours). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v27.0 - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Maps: Seasonal mean difference from observations over Europe

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_CCCma-CanESM2_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CNRM-ALADIN63_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CNRM-ALADIN63_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CNRM-ALADIN63_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

CNRM-ALADIN63_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

DMI-HIRHAM5_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_CCCma-CanESM2_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

GERICS-REMO2015_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

IPSL-WRF381P_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

KNMI-RACMO22E_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MPI-CSC-REMO2009_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

MPI-CSC-REMO2009_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [mm/day]

SMHI-RCA4_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

UHOH-WRF361H_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

UHOH-WRF361H_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

UHOH-WRF361H_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

UHOH-WRF361H_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [mm/day]

Maps: Seasonal mean percent difference from observations over Europe

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_CCCma-CanESM2_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CNRM-ALADIN63_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CNRM-ALADIN63_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CNRM-ALADIN63_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

CNRM-ALADIN63_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

DMI-HIRHAM5_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_CCCma-CanESM2_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

GERICS-REMO2015_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

ICTP-RegCM4-6_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

IPSL-WRF381P_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

KNMI-RACMO22E_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MPI-CSC-REMO2009_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

MPI-CSC-REMO2009_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r2i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r3i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

SMHI-RCA4_NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

UHOH-WRF361H_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

UHOH-WRF361H_MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

UHOH-WRF361H_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

UHOH-WRF361H_MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1 pr [% of mm/day in obs]

Maps: Change in seasonal mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CanESM2 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MIROC5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P EC-EARTH r12i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P NorESM1-M r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r12i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r3i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

Maps: Change in seasonal mean between 2070-2099 and 1991-2020 relative to 1991-2020

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CanESM2 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MIROC5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P EC-EARTH r12i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P NorESM1-M r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r2i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r3i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H EC-EARTH r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H MIROC5 r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

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